

Conference Abstract

On the elusive origin of the wild goat *Capra aegagrus* Erxleben, 1777, on the island of Montecristo (Italy)

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Abstract

Several authors stated that a “goats from the - not better identified - kingdom of Montenegro” were imported by king Vittorio Emanuele III on the small Tyrrhenian island of Montecristo at the end of the 19th century, with the aim of restocking the local big game. The Italian king had very close relations with this Balkan state and, in 1896, Montecristo became the honeymoon destination of him (at that time crown prince) and Elena, the daughter of the ruler of Montenegro. After 1899, the island became a royal hunting ground for Vittorio Emanuele's exclusive use. It cannot be excluded that a legend of the importation of Montenegrin goats onto the small Tyrrhenian island was probably born at that time. The question arises as to what species this caprine from Montenegro might have been. In fact, no evidence seems to be available on the historic natural dispersion of *C. aegagrus* in the Balkan peninsula.

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